

TILSHUNOSLIKNING AMALIY MASALALARI: ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIKNING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI, YECHIMLARI, TARAQQIYOTI VA ISTIQBOLLARI

mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman

MATERIALLARI

2025-yil 29-30-sentabr

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY TA’LIM, FAN VA
INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI
SIRDARYO VILOYATI HOKIMLIGI
GULISTON DAVLAT UNIVERSITETI,
TURKIYA RESPUBLIKASI BALIKESIR UNIVERSITETI,
TURKIYA RESPUBLIKASI FIRAT UNIVERSITETI,
YANGLING KASB-HUNAR VA TEXNIKA KOLLEJI**

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To‘plamga keltirilgan ma’ruza tezislarning mazmuni, undagi ma’lumotlar va me’yoriy hujjatlar hamda fikr-mulohazalar, takliflarning to‘g‘riligiga mualliflarning o‘zlari mas’uldirlar

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COMMUNICATION AND IDENTITY IN A GLOBALIZED WORLD

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola madaniyatlararo muloqot jarayoni va madaniy identifikatsiya masalalariga bag‘ishlangan. Muallif madaniy identifikatsiyaning ahamiyatini va uni saqlash zaruratini ta’kidlaydi, shuningdek, odamlarning boshqa madaniyatlarga integratsiya qilish jarayonini ko‘rib chiqadi. Madaniyat konstant sifatida turli ijtimoiy va madaniy guruhlar o‘rtasidagi farqlarni anglashga yordam beradi. Madaniy identifikatsiya shaxsning o‘zini boshqasidan farqli ravishda qabul qilishi, shu bilan birga, o‘zligini saqlab qolish zaruriyati borligini belgilaydi. Ushbu maqola madaniy identifikatsiya va madaniyatlararo muloqot jarayonlari o‘rtasidagi murakkab munosabatlarni ochib beradi.

Kalit so‘z va iboralar: madaniy identifikatsiya, madaniyatlararo muloqot, madaniyat, o‘zlik, ijtimoiy guruhlar

Annotation. This article is dedicated to the issues of intercultural communication and cultural identity. The author emphasizes the importance of cultural identity and the necessity to maintain it while also exploring the process of integrating into foreign cultures. Cultural identity aids in understanding the

differences between various social and cultural groups. It signifies an individual's acceptance of their distinctiveness amid others, while simultaneously necessitating the preservation of one's own identity. The article sheds light on the complex relationship between cultural identity and the processes of intercultural communication.

Keywords and expressions: cultural identity, intercultural communication, culture, self-identity, social groups

In the process of intercultural communication, every individual simultaneously addresses two crucial problems: the desire to maintain their cultural identity while engaging with foreign cultures.

In the broadest sense, «identity» refers to an individual's awareness of their belonging to a particular sociocultural group, enabling them to determine their place within the sociocultural space and navigate the surrounding world freely. The necessity for identity arises from the fact that each person needs a certain order in their life activities, which can only be provided by a community of other people. To achieve this, they must voluntarily accept the dominant elements of consciousness, tastes, habits, norms, values, and other means of interaction that are accepted among others in that community. The assimilation of these elements of social life within the group gives an individual's life an organized and predictable character, making them part of the corresponding culture.

Since every individual can simultaneously be a member of several social and cultural communities, different types of identity are typically distinguished based on the type of group affiliation: professional, civic, ethnic, political, religious, and cultural identity. Among all these types, cultural identity is of particular interest to us, which can be defined as «an individual's belonging to any culture or cultural group that shapes their value relationship to themselves, other people, society, and the world as a whole.» [Sadokhin A.P. *Mejkulturnaya kommunikatsiya*. M., 2004. P.57]

Thus, the essence of cultural identity lies in the conscious acceptance by the individual of the corresponding cultural norms and behavior models, value orientations, and language, as well as in the understanding of their self from the perspective of the cultural characteristics that are accepted in that society, identifying themselves with the cultural models of that particular society.

In intercultural communication, the problematic nature of cultural identity is based on the division of representatives of all cultures into «us» and «them.» This opposition permeates all aspects of culture and reflects the collective, mass, popular, and national worldview. Depending on the size of the collective we are considering, we can find a distinct but always clear distinction between «us» and «them.» The opposition of «us» and «them» is by no means a modern phenomenon. [Fasmer M, *Etimologicheskiy slovar russkogo yazyka: V 4-kh tt.: T. 3*. M., 1987. P 582-583]. It has divided families, clans, and tribes in archaic societies, religious sects, and so on. Conceptually, it already distinguished the «own people» from the «not one's own,» the «other,» and the «foreign,» because «own» means «belonging,» «special,» «personal,» «separate,» significant «self,» having «essence.» [Shanskiy, N. M.,

Ivanov, V. V., & Shanskaya, T. V. *Kratkiy etimologicheskiy slovar russkogo yazyka* M.,1971.P 497,419]

In the process of intercultural communication, an individual inevitably faces the question of where the boundary lies between the culture they consider their own and those cultures that are foreign to them. Answering this question is not as simple as it may seem at first glance. The connection to one's own culture is not automatically guaranteed by mere blood ties or inherited genes. This connection is established not through biological means but in some other way, which means it has a non-biological origin. One can be Uzbek by blood yet not be Uzbek in terms of culture, and vice versa. So, what serves as the foundation for this connection?

When there are many cultures, knowledge about them and existence within one of them do not necessarily coincide. One can know about Islam without being a Muslim. Knowledge and being diverge from one another. Knowledge makes a person learned, but it does not indicate their cultural belonging. It is somewhat neutral in relation to the boundary that separates «my culture» from the foreign. From what a person knows about a culture, one cannot conclude who they are culturally.

In intercultural communication, a classic situation occurs when representatives of different cultures encounter culturally specific views of the world during communication, where each partner initially fails to recognize the significance of the differences in these views, as each considers their own perceptions to be normal while viewing the perceptions of their interlocutor as abnormal.

Metaphorically speaking, when interacting with a representative of another culture, an individual is akin to traveling to a foreign country. They step outside the boundaries of their familiar environment and the circle of well-known concepts, venturing into an unfamiliar world that is enticing due to its novelty. On one hand, the foreign land is unknown and appears dangerous; on the other hand, everything new is appealing, promising new knowledge and experiences, and broadening one's horizons and life experiences.

In the modern world, the number of people crossing the boundaries of their cultural worlds and attempting to settle in another cultural region is growing. They face the choice of assimilation—potentially dissolving completely into the foreign culture—or integration, which involves a degree of adaptation while retaining their own cultural identity.

Regardless of the choice made, this process will not be easy. For culture is not just language, customs, and so on; it is also manifested in social structure, the predominant mode of material production, and other factors.

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**MAKTAB TA'LIMIDA INNOVATSION PEDAGOGIK
TEXNOLOGIYALARNI JORIY ETISH (INGLIZ TILIDAGI
EKVIVALENTSIZ LEKSIKA MISOLIDA)**

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Annotatsiya. Zamonaviy sharoitda ekvivalentsiz leksika o'qitilishi til madaniyati va tarixini o'rganishda, o'quvchilarning dunyoqarashini kengaytirishda muhim ekanligi aniqlangan. Til o'rgatishda madaniyat va til bir butun ekanligi, shuning uchun ekvivalentsiz leksikaning o'qitilishi bilan bog'liq pedagogik yondashuvlar va texnologiyalar ahamiyatiga e'tibor qaratish zarurligi ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: ekvivalentsiz leksika; lingvodidaktika; chet tilini o'qitish; pedagogik texnologiya; multimedia vositalari; madaniy realiyalar; o'quv-tarbiyaviy jarayon.

Abstract: In modern conditions, it has been determined that teaching non-equivalent vocabulary is important for studying language culture and history and for broadening students' worldview. It is emphasized that language and culture are inseparable in language teaching; therefore, attention should be paid to the significance of pedagogical approaches and technologies related to the teaching of non-equivalent vocabulary.

Keywords: non-equivalent vocabulary; linguodidactics; foreign language teaching; pedagogical technology; multimedia tools; cultural realia; educational process.

Ekvivalentsiz leksika – ya'ni ma'nosi boshqa tilda to'g'ridan to'g'ri ekvivalenti bo'lmagan so'z yoki ifoda – til va madaniyat o'rtasidagi aloqani ko'rsatadigan muhim til birliklaridandir [tilvaadabiyot.uz]. Maslova til o'ziga xos madaniy voqea-hodisalarni ifodalovchi “ekvivalentsiz leksika va lakunalar” qatlami mavjudligini ta'kidlaydi [tilvaadabiyot.uz]. Bunday so'zlar ko'pincha muayyan millat tarixiga, urf-odatlariga, tabiiy-sharoitlarga yoki diniy-afsonalarga bog'liq bo'ladi. Masalan, Mirzaaliyev va Oxunov ta'kidlashicha, ingliz tilida katta miqdordagi leksik birlikning o'zbek tilida ekvivalenti yo'q bo'lib, bu tushunchalar, avvalo, madaniy realiyalar orqali o'z ifodasini topadi. Shuning uchun ekvivalentsiz leksikani o'qitish o'quvchilarda milliy o'zlikni anglash va tilga oid madaniy kompetensiyani shakllantirish uchun zarurdir.

Chet tilini o'rgatishda so'z boyligini to'g'ri tashkil etish pedagogik jarayonning muhim bo'g'inidir. Biror tilning leksik fondi tafovutlari turli tillar o'rtasida to'liq ekvivalent o'zgarishini ta'minlamaydi – bu holatni Arifova ham qayd etadi: ikki